
SDG 4: A Review of Challenges - Bangladesh Perspective

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Abstract: Education is one of the most important factors for the development of human potential as well as socio-economic growth of every country. In Bangladesh it is also a constitutional right of the citizen. SDG 4 is one of 17 Global Goals that make up the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Achieving inclusive and quality education for all confirm the belief that education is one of the most powerful and proven vehicles for sustainable development. The main objective of the present study is to show the major challenges that hinder the success of SDG 4 in Bangladesh. Descriptive research method was employed and mostly secondary data were considered to conduct the study. It was found that at every stages of education there remain some challenges i.e. Poverty, lack of quality, lack of equal emphasis on each sector of education, insufficiency of education institutions and education materials; discrimination in the method of education system, inadequate proportion of education budget, non-availability of education loan, loss due to natural disaster etc. Finally the study recommends some suggestions to overcome these challenges.

Keywords: SDGs, SDG 4, Education, Challenge, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) sponsored by the United Nations (UN), also known as the Global Goals or Agenda 2030, are a universal call of action to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure that all people, irrespective of their country of origin, enjoy peace and prosperity [1]. It's been formally accepted by all countries and is now applicable to all, in accordance with their own national realities, capacities, levels of development, respecting national policies, priorities and environmental challenges.

Education is a fundamental human right and is indispensable for the achievement of sustainable development. Ensuring quality education is one of the major agendas to be achieved in the SDGs. SDG 4 -To ensure "inclusive and equitable education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all" is one of the 17 SDGs. A number of targets and indicators of quality education are broadly referred to the SDG 4. It has seven targets about what is to be done and three means for achieving the targets. The targets cover primary to tertiary education, technical and vocational education, skills development of youth and adults, literacy and numeracy of population, inclusiveness and equity in education, quality of education and teachers as well as provisions, scope and character of education services that address the targets. Education is at the heart of the 2030 Agenda and SDG 4 also recognized as an impartial goal. The success of other SDGs is also linked with this goal. Now it is time to focus on ensuring quality education at all levels and promoting skill-based education to face the challenges of 21st century and meet the requirements of the competitive job market. The government of Bangladesh has already managed to expand pre-primary and primary education at rural areas through some effective initiatives and programs in line with SDG 4 so as to make development consistent and sustainable. As part of diverse initiatives, the government gradually is trying to implement "National Education Policy 2010" step by step because it has to face the challenges of 21st century as well as build well educated and technologically skilled human resources. Despite various government efforts and progress achieved in the education sector in different dimensions, significant challenges also remain that acts as the major obstacle of development.

2. Objectives of the study

This paper focuses specifically on the education agenda of SDG 4. The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To highlight the challenges of SDG 4 in Bangladesh.
- To give an overview of SDG 4.
- To recommend some suggestions to overcome the challenges of SDG 4 those accelerate the achievement and smooth progress of the goal.

3. Methodology

The main objective of the paper is to show the challenges of SDG 4. Along with the main objective the study also gives an overview on SDG 4 in Bangladesh as well as some recommendations also given on the basis of findings. Descriptive research method is used to attain the objectives. With this perception, relevant data were collected from secondary sources. To collect secondary data, a number of government reports, frameworks, guidelines, publications of Ministry/Division; published statistical data from reliable and recognized sources were reviewed. Also several books, articles, website and some news papers etc. were collected and reviewed to get clear idea about the topic of the study with respect to objectives mentioned above.

4. Literature Review

The ultimate goal of the SDGs is the most important that of “Transforming the World”. Lesson from history in the development of countries and societies has shown practically that education is central to achieving these goals. We cannot transform our world and achieve the other SDGs without achieving its goal 4 on education. The SDG 4 reflects the important role of education by encapsulating significant targets.

Education is a fundamental human right and closely linked to the realization of other rights. It is like a public good for all individual and base for human fulfillment, peace, sustainable development, gender inequality and responsible global citizenship. As a vehicle for development, education is a key contributor to reducing inequality and scaling down poverty. Access to quality education at all levels is an essential condition for accelerating progress towards the achievement of other sustainable development goals [2].

Ensuring inclusive and equitable education is really a challenge for any developing country in the world, for Bangladesh it would be more challenge due to lack of quality teachers, large classroom, less knowledge on ICT and skill based education [3].

Around 4 million out of schoolchildren at the primary level throughout the country with specific groups of children facing greater constraints to complete primary level-these include working children, disabled children, indigenous children and children living in remote areas or slums or living in poverty, is a huge challenge to attain the targets of SDG [4].

Early childhood development and education is very much important for the children to becoming good citizen for the country in future. The Multiple indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) 2019 revealed that only 19% of children in age 36 to 59 months have participated in some form of organized early childhood development [5]. One in every five children dropped out of school in 2016 due to high levels of poverty, child marriage, social insecurity and marginalization.[6]. The proportion of girls completed primary education is not equally seen in the secondary level education. Poverty, early marriage, unawareness of guardians, misapprehension of religion, lack of communication, eve teasing and violence against girls, poverty, are among the reasons of their lagging behind[3].High dropout rate is a major challenge in secondary education. Though incentives in the form of stipends, free textbooks, and free meal programs are being provided, the dropout rate is disheartening. Only 46 percent of students complete the full cycle of secondary education, reflecting a huge waste of financial resources and an inefficient education system [7].

The participation in technical and Vocational Education (TVET) is unsatisfactory. Basically, students and parents have the fascination to the mainstream and academy based education and very few have the choice of enrolling in TVET. Although the public expenditure on education is around 2 per cent of Bangladesh’s GDP which is one of the lowest in South Asia and among the developing countries[3].

The enrollment in tertiary education in Bangladesh stands at around 17 percent in 2016 trailing behind neighboring countries such as India 27 percent and Sri Lanka 19 percent and not up to the average of lower-middle-income country[8]. At present employers are demanding higher skilled professionals for technical and managerial positions to support the growing industry and service sectors but tertiary education institutes (TEIs) are struggling to produce employable graduates for the job market. In Bangladesh TEIs do not encourage critical thinking and primarily utilize rote-learning

which encourages passivity. As a result, employers do not get the skill sets they require from graduates [9]. There exists a gap between skill demand side (Firms) with skills supply side (TEIs).

Bangladesh is on its way to become a Middle Income Country (MIC) in 2026 and will become a developed country by 2041. We cannot be a real middle-income country if a large proportion of young people are without a high school education. Without forming a pathways towards creating a knowledge-based economy and society then the country will not become a developed country by 2041[10].

Education is refers as a character building process, enhancing one’s personality and making him/her rational, capable, responsive and intelligent. Teachers have more responsibilities in molding the character of the students. Thus, the role of the teacher in the society is vital for its development. The quality of education depends on the quality of teachers [11].

For achieving the SDG 4 through developing our government policies, rules, regulations and programs; also, a review of ESD may be considered in those reformations. An expertise effort is required at different levels of policy making in the country. Moreover, new programs might be offered presently providing a good basis of sustainable development criteria in inter-sector collaboration, such as managing interlinked opportunities among educational policies, curricula, teachers’ capacity and student appraisal [12].

ESD can help to reduce the negative impacts due to developments through creating the sustainability competencies among the learners. This education helps the people to take proper decision for environmental balance, economic well-beings and social justice for present and future generations. It makes interactive, learning outcome settings and learner-centered teaching experiences for the learners as well as includes the issues as climate change, poverty and sustainable consumption practices in the curricula. It assists to the individuals for achieving SDGs through their competencies and necessary knowledge on transformational and understandable perception on sustainable development [13].

Successful attainments of SDG 4 help the developing countries to accelerate the path of development. The Government of Bangladesh takes tremendous initiative to achieve the targets of SDG 4 as well as to overcome the challenges remains there.

5. Sustainable Development Goal 4: Outcome Targets and Means of Implementation

Education is a process by which our mind, soul and body get developed through a formal learning. It is much crucial for human being for every kind of development. Due to the education process our physical and mental capabilities are developed in an objective way. Education helps us to develop different kind of abilities like thinking, sensibility etc. SDG 4 includes seven targets and three means of implementation which aim to ensure quality education for sustainable development.

SDG 4 : Outcome Targets	Meaning of Targets
<p>4.1. Quality primary & secondary education By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes.</p>	<p>The provision of 12 years of free, publicly-funded, inclusive, equitable, quality primary and secondary education – of which at least nine years are compulsory, leading to relevant learning outcomes – should be ensured for all, without discrimination.</p>
<p>4.2. Early childhood & pre- primary education By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education.</p>	<p>The provision of at least one year of free and compulsory quality pre-primary education is encouraged, to be delivered by well-trained educators, as well as that of early childhood development and care.</p>
<p>4.3 Equal access to TVET & higher education By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university</p>	<p>It is imperative to reduce barriers to skills development and technical and vocational education and training (TVET), starting from the secondary level, as well as to tertiary education, including university, and to provide lifelong learning opportunities for youth and adults. The provision of tertiary education should be made progressively free, in line with existing international agreements.</p>
<p>4.4 Relevant skills for work By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Access: Equitable access to TVET needs to be expanded while quality is ensured. Learning opportunities should be increased and diversified, using a wide range of education and training modalities. Skills acquisition: Beyond work-specific skills, emphasis must be placed on developing high-level cognitive and non-cognitive/transferable skills, such as problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, teamwork, communication skills and conflict resolution.</p>

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<p>4.5 Gender equality & equal access for all By 2030, eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children in vulnerable situations.</p>	<p>Inclusion and equity: All people, irrespective of sex, age, race, color, ethnicity, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property or birth, as well as persons with disabilities, migrants, indigenous peoples, and children and youth, especially those in vulnerable situations or other status, should have access to inclusive, equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities.</p> <p>Gender equality: All girls and boys, women and men, should have equal opportunity to enjoy education of high quality, achieve at equal levels and enjoy equal benefits from education. Adolescent girls and young women, who may be subject to gender-based violence, child marriage, early pregnancy and a heavy load of household chores, as well as those living in poor and remote rural areas, require special attention. In contexts in which boys are disadvantaged, targeted action should be taken for them. Policies aimed at overcoming gender inequality are more effective when they are part of an overall package that also promotes health, justice, <u>good governance and freedom from child labor.</u></p>
<p>4.6 Youth & adult literacy By 2030, ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults both men and women achieve literacy and numeracy</p>	<p>Action for this target aims at ensuring that by 2030, all young people and adults across the world should have achieved relevant and recognized proficiency levels in functional literacy and numeracy skills that are equivalent to levels achieved at successful completion of basic education.</p>
<p>4.7 Education for sustainable development and global citizenship By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship an appreciation of culture diversity and of culture’s contribution to sustainable development</p>	<p>The knowledge, skills, values and attitudes required by citizens to lead productive lives, make informed decisions and assume active roles locally and globally in facing and resolving global challenges can be acquired through education for sustainable development and global citizenship education, which includes peace and human rights education, as well as intercultural education and education for international understanding.</p>
<p>Means of Implementation 4. a) Effective learning environments Build and upgrade education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all</p>	<p>This target addresses the need for adequate physical infrastructure and safe, inclusive environments that nurture learning for all, regardless of background or disability status.</p>
<p>4.b) Scholarships for higher education By 2020, substantially expand globally the number of scholarships available to developing countries, in particular to least developed countries, small- island developing States and African countries for enrolment in higher education, including vocational training and information and communications technology, technical, engineering and scientific programs, in developed countries and other developing countries.</p>	<p>Where developed countries offer scholarships to students from developing countries, these should be structured to build the capability of the developing country. While the importance of scholarships is recognized, donor countries are encouraged to increase other forms of support to education. In line with the SDG4-Education 2030 focus on equity, inclusion and quality, scholarships should be transparently targeted at young people from disadvantaged backgrounds.</p>
<p>4.c) Teachers and educators By 2030, substantially increase the supply of qualified teachers, including through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, especially least developed countries and small island developing States</p>	<p>Teachers are the key to achieving all of the SDG4 targets. It requires urgent attention, because the equity gap in education is exacerbated by the shortage and uneven distribution of professionally trained teachers, especially in disadvantaged areas. As teachers are a fundamental condition for guaranteeing quality education, teachers and educators should be empowered, adequately recruited and remunerated, motivated, professionally qualified, and supported within well-resourced, efficient and effectively governed systems.</p>

Source: UNESCO’s Unpacking Sustainable Development Goal 4[14].

In Bangladesh SDG 4 is recognized as an impartial goal and the success of other SDGs- such as those related to health, growth and employment, sustainable consumption and production, climate change and humanitarian response, peace, justice and good governance is also linked with this goal [15]. As a vehicle for development, education is a key contributor to reducing inequality and scaling down poverty. Thus access to quality education at all levels is an essential condition for accelerating progress towards the achievement of other sustainable development goals.

Relationship of SDG 4 with other SDGs.

6. Challenges

Education in Bangladesh has three major stages- primary, secondary and higher educations. Primary level education is provided through two major institutional arrangements - general and madrasa, while secondary education has three major streams: general, technical-vocational and madrasa. Higher education, also, has 3 streams: general (inclusive of pure and applied science, arts, business and social science), madrasa and technology education [16]. Ensuring inclusive, equitable and quality education is really a challenge for any developing country in the world like Bangladesh. These include inclusive and equitable education & quality of education at all levels; quality of teaching, adult literacy and lifelong learning, corruption, frequent leakage of question paper; insufficiency of education institutions; discrimination in the method of education system; lack of quality teachers and educational materials; inadequate budget, high teacher-student ratio; larger class room size; shortage of trained teachers; lack of accountability etc. Challenges that exist at different steams of education system in Bangladesh are:

6.1 Primary Level:

- A large number of children are left behind from enrolled in the public school system although primary education is free and the textbooks are provided by the government. These includes - children with disabilities; children living in tea garden; children from ethnic minority communities; children from lower caste communities; children of commercial sex workers; children engaged in child labor; children with extreme poor socio-economic condition, children living in geographically hard to reach areas- char, haor, slums, hills and coastal area etc.
- Discrimination in the method of education system among different types of primary education institutions - community schools, non-registered schools, registered schools, government schools, kindergartens & urban and rural schools.
- Poor teaching methods, incompetent and untrained teachers, lack of encouragement and inspiration has caused children to not continue their schooling.
- Lack of development of children in physically, intellectually, socially and emotionally is a major constraint in primary level. Until now the under five aged children are not getting proper developmental support from the government. Lack of proper implementation of pre-primary education is also a major reason of not achieving quality primary education in Bangladesh.
- Though Indigenous children received textbooks in their mother tongues; new teachers with expertise on alphabets of indigenous languages have not been appointed, and existing teachers have not been provided with adequate training.

6.2 Secondary Level & Higher Secondary Level:

- High dropout rate in the secondary level is a big challenge. Major reasons behind the existing dropout are physical disability, poverty, child marriage, social insecurity, gender preference etc.
- Regional discrimination among different educational institutions also a major challenge. There is a gap between the education provided in urban and the education provided in rural areas. Also there exists difference in education cost between urban and rural as well as public and private institutions. Students with extreme poor socio-economic condition are unable to continue.
- Insufficiency of secondary education institutions; frequent leakage of question paper; lack of quality and trained teachers; shortage of education materials; high teacher-student ratio; large class room size etc. are also the pressing

challenges in secondary education sector in Bangladesh.

- Lack of effective focus on TVET, second chance education for dropped out and missed out learners also a crucial factor in secondary level.
- Among the 7052 technical and vocational institutions, Majority institutions (87.27%) were privately managed and only 12.73% were publicly managed [16]. As a result students from poorer background are unable to participate in technical and vocational education.
- The marketing and branding initiatives for Technical and Vocational Education is not adequate; government can't attract mass population to this education. The participation in technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is unsatisfactory and also gender based discrimination remains here.
- Lack of public institutions in higher secondary level is also a major challenge. Though the total institution involved in college education has been increasing but majority (86%) are privately managed and only 14 % are government managed [16].

6.3 Tertiary Level:

- Lack of quality education is a major challenge in tertiary level. Our mindsets to the result based education system rather than building the learning process for achieving emotional intelligence - ethics, honesty, transparency, accountability etc in the career path. The process sometimes foolishly locks the creativity and brainstorming activities of learners'.
- Lack of collaboration- academic and research, among the universities in domestic and international level. As a result, research output is considerably lower than those of other neighboring countries.
- Lack of University- Industry linkage address the challenges that tertiary education institutions fail to create graduates according to skill sets require by the employers.
- In Bangladesh, gross enrollment rate in TEIs is lower than those of our South Asian neighbors; also it is much lower than the other Middle-Income Countries (MIC). Moreover the proportion of female students at TEIs is lower than that of males[9].
- Insufficient accommodation facility is another problem in tertiary level. According to Annual Education Survey (AES) 2019, the total students of 45 public Universities were 818040. Among them 101214 (12.37 %) were resident students and 87.63% were non-resident students. Among 101214 resident students only 39515 girls (39.04 %) were resident students as against 38% of girl students in the total enrolment in the public universities [16].
- Political involvement, session jam, corruption and lack of accountability & good governance at tertiary level also influence the quality and smooth conduction of education.
- No national student loan facilities or financial assistance exists to help students from poorer backgrounds to access tertiary education. Scholarships and waivers are the major means of financial assistance that are inadequate.

6.4 Madrasah Education:

Madrasah education is a subsector of education system in Bangladesh and popularly known as religious stream and quite distinct from the general stream. This subsector is also large, catering to over 3.80 million students. Ebtedayee madrasah offers primary equivalent while post-primary madrasah covers Dakhil, Alim, Fazil and Kamil; which are equivalent to secondary, Higher Secondary, Degree and Masters Education of general stream. Madrasahs are absolutely privately managed which is the major challenge for smooth education. In 2019 a total of 9278 madrasahs offered Dakhil to Kamil education. Among 9278 madrasahs 9275 (99.96%) were privately managed [16].

6.5 Teacher Education:

The quality of education depends on the quality of teachers. Teachers' education is provided by seven types of educational institutions. These are: Primary Training Institutes (PTIs), Teachers Training College (TTC), Technical Teacher Training College (TTTC), Vocational Teacher Training Institute (VTTI), Physical Education College, Higher Secondary Teacher Training Institute (HSTTI) and Bangladesh Madrasahs Teacher Training Institute (BMTTI). Slow growth and insufficiency of this sector is also a big challenge in quality education .The total number of institutions was 129 in 2000, 143 in 2003, 215 in 2015 and 216 in 2019. Among 216 institutions, 39% were government and 61% were privately managed [16].

6.6 Natural Disaster/Calamity:

It is well recognized that Bangladesh would be one of the most adversely affected countries to climate change. It is prone to disasters such as surge, floods, cyclone, water logging, salinity, earthquake, river erosion, drought, etc. [17]. In every year many hazards/losses found in education sector due to climate change and disaster. In 2019, a total of 25430 educational institutions found affected by natural disaster (like surge cyclone, flood, salinity, water logging etc.) consists of 1405 government and 24025 non government institutions including primary, junior secondary, secondary, madrasah, and college[16].

6.7 Impact of COVID - 19 on Education:

Education sector, which is the backbone of a country, has been affected by pandemic of COVID-19. Nearly 38 million students in Bangladesh have missed out the opportunity to receive learning and interact with their peers due to the closure of schools on March 2020 as part of the measures taken to slow the spread of COVID-19. Government introduced remote learning through radio, television, mobile phone and internet to help students' deal with the adverse impact of school closure [18]. Distance learning or online learning has been a productive measure in this global pandemic crisis for many countries. But in our country, not all students have access to these opportunities due to digital divide between the rich & the poor households. Unequal accesses to educational resources to different level of students are creating barriers to their learning process. As a result, though the online learning process impacts the overall outcome of the education system [19]. These impacts also affect the achievement of the targets of SDG 4.

7. Recommendation

Education is a key determinant of social and economic transformation, and an essential domain to peace, tolerance and sustainability. To overcome the challenges of SDG 4, the study recommends the following suggestions:

- ❖ At present the gross enrollment rate (GER) and net enrollment rate (NER) to primary education is remarkable but the quality of education is a matter of concern. So the responsible authority must take necessary initiatives to ensure the quality of education at primary level. Also adequate and strong focus should be given to early childhood development.
- ❖ Ensure formal and non formal education for children with disabilities; children living in tea garden; children from ethnic minority communities; children from lower caste communities; children of commercial sex workers; children engaged in child labor; children with extreme poor socio-economic condition, children living in geographically hard to reach areas etc.
- ❖ Secondary school enrolment rates lag behind than primary completion rates. Only 30% students can complete 12 grade education and 70% of the students' dropout from education in secondary level [3]. As the country aspires to reach the stage of a developed economy within 2041, ensure at least grade 12 education for all students. So more efforts are needed to increase the enrollment of secondary and higher secondary level.
- ❖ To reform the education system in line with the needs of the modern labor market TVET needs to become flexible and market driven, gender gap need to be reduced and access to rural population in vocational education need to be increased. More marketing and promotional program need to be introduced for attaining the popularity of TVET.
- ❖ Majority of Technical and Vocational Education institutions (87.27%) were privately managed and only 12.73% were publicly managed [16].To increase the participation in technical and vocational education, number of publicly managed institution need to be increased.
- ❖ To achieve the targets of goal 4 of SDGs equal emphasis should be put on general, madrasha, vocational and technical education. In junior and secondary level the portion of publicly managed institutions is very low. It must be increased. The Rural and urban inequality in education system must be minimized.
- ❖ For creating employable graduates TEIs need to do more on improving soft skills and higher-order cognitive skills into the curriculum to develop graduates. Special focus should be given in areas of critical thinking, problem-solving, communications, information and communication technology (ICT) skills etc. As well as ensure impartiality in teaching, student assessment and research, employment and promotions are based on legal, transparent and objective criteria.
- ❖ Increase the collaboration among the universities in domestic and international level which increase the knowledge share and increase the research output. Establish University- Industry linkage to overcome the challenges of job market for employable graduates.
- ❖ Increase the accommodation facility in public universities and create avenues of national loan facilities or financial assistance for students at tertiary level. This will help the students from poorer backgrounds to access tertiary education.

- ❖ Quality is the central theme in education systems. The quality of education is judged by focusing on students' performance, what they actually learn, and how well they learn it. The quality of education depends on the quality, skills, capability and dedication of teachers. Increase the training facility for primary, secondary, college and madrasa teacher and integrate ESD curricula in teacher education & training modules. Also the number of publicly managed training institutions should be increased.
- ❖ Implementing authority of SDG 4 are - Ministry of Primary and Mass Education, Secondary and Higher Education Division, Technical and Madrasah Division, Economic Relations Divisions. Existence of a strong institutional support and coordination is must among these responsible authorities for leading, coordinating, monitoring & controlling the mechanism of successful implementation of SDG 4.
- ❖ Ensure adequate budget for education i.e 15-20 per cent of the national budget and 4-6 per cent of GDP. The public expenditure on education is around 2/3 percent of Bangladesh's GDP as well as 10-14% of national budget which is inadequate to cover all of its necessities to ensure quality education for all [16].
- ❖ Integrate and implement the ESD curricula in all formal education including primary, secondary, technical, vocational education and training (TVET) and higher education.
- ❖ Bangladesh, being one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change, needs to incorporate effects of climate change in national development plans. Necessary initiatives have taken by the government and the individual institution for increasing the capability to recover the impact of disaster. New policies - adaptation strategies with climate change need to be developed and existing policies to be strengthened which moderates the harm.
- ❖ Develop effective remedial learning opportunities and ensure the implementation of the same to mitigate the losses sustained at all levels of education during the pandemic of COVID-19.
- ❖ For successful achievement of SDG 4 only the effort from government is not actually enough; need joint actions from multi-stakeholder partnership, civil society organizations as well as corporate sector to achieve the targets. Ensure active participation of NGO and other civil society organizations in country's education delivery system.
- ❖ To achieve the goal (SDG 4), the government needs to establish good governance at educational institutions and curb corruption in this sector.

8. Conclusion

From the very beginning, Bangladesh is showing strong commitment to achieve the targets of Agenda 2030 and SDG 4 is the heart of these agenda. Achieving SDG 4 will help to achieve the other SDGs.

Education is significant in shaping individual and collective knowledge, skills, values and attitudes to enable people to move along pathways towards sustainable development. The major aim of SDG 4 is to provide an inclusive and high quality education which will improve the learner's standard of living, and the country's future. It's needed a comprehensive and rigorous plan of action to achieve the targets of SDG 4. Besides government, we need to leverage partnerships between government, non-government, private sector, and civil society in managing education delivery. Every educational institution must have their own strategic plan to align with the demand of SDGs. Moreover, special attention should be given to four development areas - policies, curricula, teacher and student.

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